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Abstract for ICCM19

“50 Years of Advanced Composites Research and Innovation: A Canadian Perspective”

Plenary Lecture in Honour of the Scala Awardee, Dr. Ken Street

Advanced composites have now been with us for some 50 years, and their rate of adoption has increased dramatically in recent years. Since the very beginning it has been clear that composites can offer significant benefits, all essentially linked to the fact that raw material and final structure are created at the same time. But the complexity that leads to this benefit has also been the root cause of the risk and uncertainty that has plagued their adoption. In this context, this lecture traces the history of composites research and innovation in Canada. The aim is not only to honour the contributions of the 2013 Scala Awardee, Dr. Ken Street, but also to start a dialogue on key indicators and issues that have affected composites research and innovation over the last 50 years.